

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ABUBAKR-BIBILAZU****FIRST NAME: SAFIYATU****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., Microsoft 365 on Windows 11)

List your 5 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Key essentials for academic essay writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 1-16)
2. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34-39)
3. American and British English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 25-32)
4. Style Guide (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 41-57)
5. Referencing (Cleenewerck 2016, 2; Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 35 and 38)

HOW TO WRITE AN ACADEMIC PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401D course pack for period one documents the key requirements for academic writing. The course material recaps academic writing in a chronological manner and with comprehensive details. It gives students a good foundation for research ethics and allows them to distinguish between American and British English for a good paper.

I was surprised by English tutoring as I studied the ACA-401D course pack for period one. However, academic writing must be clear and concise with an interesting logical sequence. Hence, it is essential to understand the nuances between American and British English for a good paper. The guidelines discussed are crucial for writing quality articles that can withstand competitive publication processes.

In this response paper, I will discuss five major concepts I learned from the ACA-401D period one course. These include key essentials for academic essay writing, American and British English language style, plagiarism, style guide, and referencing.

2) KEY ESSENTIALS FOR ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

An academic essay is a paper on a specific topic for an audience. A good academic essay must be clear and concise. This implies that the researcher must have a detailed understanding of issues to define a clear research topic and questions for investigation. In writing academic papers, I recognize the importance of credibility and coherence in writing to my audience. Therefore, I will organize my ideas sequentially to give clarity while creating a dialogue between evidence, analysis, and interpretation. Before documenting the evidence, I shall outline a detailed approach to conducting the research and provide detailed references to information. I recognize that the ACA-401D period one outlines a stepwise approach to writing a good academic essay. Notwithstanding this, my choice of the English language is vital in communicating ideas (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 7-11).

3) AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH LANGUAGE STYLE

The commonly used English languages are American and British English. The use of either American or British English by countries is associated with colonization. British colonized countries use British English while American colonized countries use American English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 25).

Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024, 25-32) demonstrated the existing variation in the two languages. For instance, single quotation marks are used for British English, whereas double quotation marks are used for American English. Similarly, the use of grammar, syntax, and punctuation differs for the American and English languages. I have noted the use of commas, periods, and colons in salutations and the spelling of words differently, but with the same meaning. In some instances, different expressions are used to mean the same thing in both American and British English.

I have observed that the two languages are sometimes used interchangeably in writing. This is due to the lack of in-depth knowledge of the ethical principles of American and British English. I resonate with the fact that it is unethical to have a mix of American and British English in write-ups. This is to avoid confusion and misinterpretation of the message. Therefore, at the onset of writing, one should decide on the type of English language to use and apply its ethical principles accordingly (Cleenewerck 2016, 1). I believe that the application of appropriate English language ethics will enrich academic essay writing.

4) PLAGIARISM

"Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without accreditation to the author of that source of information" (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 34). Plagiarism involves using materials, including data and/or extracts, without acknowledging the authors. It covers citation, quotations, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting of documents without acknowledging the source (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 34-37). I believe that the development of an article and the generation of data do not come easily. It requires a lot of effort to produce a good quality output that will be fulfilling for everyone. Therefore, acknowledging one's effort demonstrates gratitude for the work done. People fall prey to plagiarism due to a limited understanding of its scope. I, therefore, applaud EUCLID for outlining the details of plagiarism as part of the Ph.D. in Monitoring, Measurement, and Evaluation (DME) course. This is because it will promote creativity and ethical behavior while doing the coursework, which will be a key takeaway for research.

5) STYLE GUIDE

Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024, 41-42) detail that "a style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent."

A style guide is the backbone for all research, including academic writing and publications. I have observed that calls for proposals and publications have detailed and unique writing styles that must be strictly respected. Compliance with the style guides of proposal bids and manuscripts contributes to the acceptance of articles by prospective institutions. Therefore, I believe that training students on the use and adherence to style guides by EUCLID will nurture them with the appropriate use of acceptable guidelines. The adherence to style guides will enhance branding and professionalism in research and publication.

6) REFERENCING

Referencing provides details of information sources used in writing a paper. It comprises in-text citations and a reference list or bibliography. Typically, in-text citations document the name of the author, year, and page number, whereas the reference list provides full details of all information sources used in an article in alphabetical order (Cleenewerck 2016, 2; Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 35 and 38). I have had the opportunity to use both in-text citations and reference lists in research and academic papers. I observed differences in referencing styles and the need for consistency in the choice of styles. This also calls for adherence to recommended style guides. I perceive the Chicago style guide being used by EUCLID to be a comprehensive guide that will expose students to all aspects of writing styles for a good article (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 44-57).

7) CONCLUSION

The course on International Academic Writing is very educational and provides significant insight into academic writing. It provides a good foundation for robust articles and sets the pace for a good doctoral thesis. The course has enriched my knowledge of style guides and the choice of language for research, including academic writing. I believe that the knowledge acquired from the International Academic Writing course will contribute to shaping my thesis for the award of a Ph.D. in Monitoring, Measurement, and Evaluation.

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